

Workshop Report on the Development of the Glossary for the Learning Objectives Matrix on the Topic of Research Data Management (RDM)

V3

Workshop Report on the Development of the Glossary for the Learning Objectives Matrix on Research Data Management V3

While working on the third version of the Learning Objectives Matrix (LOM) for Research Data Management (RDM), it became clear that a glossary is necessary to clarify the terms used in the context of the LOM and to avoid misunderstandings. The editorial team selected the terms collaboratively, allowing all participants to propose relevant terms. A dedicated glossary working group developed the explanations to ensure precise and consistent terminology. To this end, a workflow was established that structures the terminology work, ensures transparency, and actively involves the entire editorial team in the coordination process.

A template was designed and iteratively refined for the terms to be explained, using selected SKOS (Simple Knowledge Organization System) concepts such as `skos:prefLabel`, `skos:scopeNote`, `skos:closeMatch`, and `skos:editorialNote`. The explanations for the terms were systematically compiled, primarily using subject-specific sources and, where appropriate, additional general but relevant reference sources. Subject-specific sources were given priority, especially those authored by experts in the respective field and ideally cited with a persistent digital identifier (e.g., DOI, Handle, URN). If no appropriate reference source could be identified from which a definition or explanation for the LOM could be quoted, adapted, or translated, an original formulation was developed.

So far, no reference has been made to other SKOS concepts when linking terms, and no structured data sources such as Wikidata entries could be used instead of Wikipedia. Therefore, the glossary often refers to simple HTML pages or PDF documents. However, since the focus is on indexing the content and making the terms comprehensible, it proves to be helpful in the context of the glossary.

A checklist of criteria was developed to ensure the quality and consistency of the term explanations. This checklist is used to review the requirements for scope notes.¹ Scope notes should fulfill the following criteria:

- be orientated towards the purpose and scope of the LOM,
- must not include synonyms or terms that are not part of the system,
- avoid homonyms and polysemes,
- be target group-orientated and stay current,
- exclude circular definitions, ramifications and redundancies,
- be neither too broad nor too narrow,
- not be formulated negatively,
- contain examples only if they contribute to comprehensibility.

This checklist was continuously expanded and discussed collaboratively with the aim of harmonizing the terminology and ensuring uniform use. In this way, the LOM editorial team developed a total of 44 explanations of terms and made them available to users in order to promote the user-friendliness, interdisciplinarity, reusability and sustainability of the LOM. The explanations of terms can be categorised as follows:

- Citations: 5
- Derived: 30
- Self-formulated: 9

These were subject to continuous linguistic revision, including the use of standardized vocabulary, the removal of abbreviations, and the formulation of concise sentences.

At the same time, a SKOS scheme was developed and continuously updated with the involvement of the community. The specific use of the vocabulary specified by SKOS was discussed with experts and in consultation with individual representatives of the digital humanities and metadata community.

In line with the practical orientation of the LOM and with a view to the heterogeneous target group from different disciplines, the aim is to develop a basic schema that enables vocabulary matching across different sources and simple categorization of these sources with SKOS. We deliberately refrained from formulating generally valid definitions (skos:definition) for terms related to research data management. Instead, the glossary entries are understood as notes, particularly application notes (skos:scopeNote), which explain how the terms are used in the context of the LOM.

Additionally, a distinction was made between direct and indirect quotation for the reference sources and the URI or DOI as well as the full citation were included in the schema. The reference sources used are recorded in a Zotero library, tagged with the respective terms and the relevant text passages are saved as notes.

¹ <https://epub.uni-regensburg.de/44951>

In the course of this development process and with the basic schema designed here, some points remain open that still need to be clarified and specified:

1. **Use of skos:exactMatch and skos:closeMach:** Both tags are currently used to refer to external sources - either in the form of a URL/URI or as a cited literature source that provides a direct or indirect quotation for the term explanations in the LOM. At present, however, the referenced sources are not standardized or formalized in SKOS but are mostly conventional internet sources.
2. **Use of skos:scopeNote:** The skos:scopeNote provides a good description of the LOM concepts and is additionally contextualised by the source references.
3. **Missing skos:broader, skos:narrower and related relations:** In this version, there are still no hierarchical relations such as skos:broader (superordinate terms) or skos:narrower (subordinate terms). The checklist defines these relationships, enabling the semantic structure to be further expanded and thereby fostering a more interconnected ontology. However, it requires a careful analysis of conceptual relationships and a clear definition of the hierarchy. Additionally, a decision must be made as to whether superordinate or subordinate terms are relevant to the LOM.
4. **Specification of skos:prefLabel in several languages:** Currently, skos:prefLabel is already used for German and English in order to add multilingualism to the LOM with regard to the planned translation.
5. **Review of the URI structure:** The community project faces the challenge of finding a sustainable solution that ensures long-term availability and consistent use of the URIs. Such a solution could include the integration of a central, trustworthy infrastructure for the allocation and management of persistent identifiers, such as a dedicated URN or DOI system. The namespace should be chosen in such a way that it enables both the cross-disciplinary expansion of the ontology and the linking with other existing data sources and ontologies without compromising flexibility for future developments. Alternatively, SkoHub offers a suitable infrastructure, as it supports the automated publication and management of vocabularies and facilitates networking with other ontologies.
6. **Revision and version control:** If the glossary entries are updated regularly, it would make sense to keep a version history or a change log in the skos:historyNote, especially in the context of a longer-term development towards an ontology.

Another important point is the fostering of interdisciplinary collaboration and further development of the glossary and, in future, the LOM. This requires the selection and establishment of an open and collaborative platform that allows the RDM community, comprised of people from various disciplines, to continuously expand and improve the

glossary. In order to ensure that the glossary remains relevant and up to date in the long term, new concepts must be incorporated into transparent workflows and existing term explanations must be adapted.

A Git repository is useful for the sustainable provision and further development of the LOM glossary, as it enables versioning, traceability and collaborative editing. With the kind support of the German Initiative for Network Information (DINI), in particular the Competence Centre for Interoperable Metadata (KIM)² working group, DINI-AG KIM for short, the 'fdm-lernziele' group was established within the DINI-AG KIM. An associated repository provides the glossary as SKOS vocabulary via SkoHub Pages³. The RDM community is warmly invited to participate in further development by holding discussions on Git and submitting contributions via pull requests and issues.

² <https://dini.de/standards>

³ <https://skohub.io/>